

An assessment of the spatial and temporal changes of Mabira tropical forest reserve and environs in Central Uganda

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Abstract

Uganda's forest cover has undergone radical changes in the past century with conflicting views of ecological benefits versus economic value. This study presents the dynamics of land use/cover changes in and around Mabira Central Forest Reserve (CFR) between 1970 and 2015 period. A series of Landsat TM/ETM+ images were used to characterize changes and socio-economic data to assess the dynamics of land use/cover changes. The classification results showed significant losses in wetlands for 1975-2000 period, while between 2000-2015 the greatest losses were realized in forest cover. The gain in land occurred in subsistence farmlands between 1975-2000 whereas between 2000 and 2015, it was seen in the built-up class. The overall image classification accuracy achieved was 100%, 100%, 79% and 76% for the years 1975, 1986, 2000 and 2015, respectively. The Logistic regression results revealed that the major drivers of land use/cover changes were: the high household size, perceived loss of soil fertility, poor agricultural practices, establishment of roadside markets, industrialization, and unclear forestry boundary ($P < 0.05$); the non-significant drivers included the low education levels, establishment of power grids, insecurity, political interference, and weak enforcement of environmental laws. This study is among those that continue to advocate for demarcation of forest boundary, enforcement of forestry laws and land use planning critical in the sustainable utilization of forest products and biodiversity conservation.

Key words: Remote sensing; land use; land cover; change detection

1.0 Introduction

Uganda, currently, has 506 Central Forest Reserves which amounts to 6.3% of the total land area. A Central Forest Reserve is a body of forest demarcated and managed by the National Forestry Authority under the National Forestry and Tree Planning Act 2003 (Odokonyero 2005). The conservation activities carried out by National Forestry Authority in the reserves include restoration, eco-tourism, collaborative management among others (Naidoo and Adamowicz, 2005). Despite, the implementation of restoration programs, the reserves are still faced with increasing pressure from a diversity of changing land use/cover types that arise from the surrounding communities and beyond from encroachment, illegal extraction of timber and malicious cutting of trees.

(NEMA, 2007); hence the economy is threatened to having no forests left by 2050 if the level of deforestation persists at the present rate (NEMA 2008). UNEP (2004) indicates that the conversion of natural land cover to cropland, grazing land, and forest plantations will continue and most at risk are natural forests which are predicted to reduce by further 38% in 2032. The depletion of natural cover has exacerbated loss of biodiversity impacting negatively on soil and water quality as well as global climatic and livelihood systems (Turner et al., 1995; Laurence, 1999; Noss, 2001; Armenteras et al., 2003).

It is estimated that over 90,000 hectares of tree cover per year are deforested mainly to create cultivatable land, increased demand for fuel wood and timber and building poles. All these factors have come into force primarily because of increasing population pressure, industrialization, political interference and trade which have undermined the ecological integrity of forests in the country (Kayanja & Byarugaba 2001, Boakye et al., 2008, Ringrose et al., 1997, Rosyadi et al., 2005). According to the population projections from (UN-DESA (2007) the population growth rates by 2025 for Uganda are (between 2.86% and 3.24%) being among the world's highest.

Mabira Forest is one of the biggest forest reserves in Uganda characterized with high forest stand and not exception to the increasing human related challenges facing its survival. The forest has been subjected to gross human encroachment that translates

way back from 1970s coming from the enclaves, surrounding communities and districts as well as the political turmoil with minimum encroachment realized between 1988 and 1989 when all the encroachers were evicted (Baranga, 2007; Nabanoga et al., 2010). The forest continues to support the communities with firewood, medicinal plants, eco-tourism, modification of climate, building poles, wild fruits among others. However, given the goods and services that are offered by the forest, it is threatened by the increasing population pressure, political interferences, industrialization, road side markets and weak enforcement which have adversely affected the forest, particularly the biodiversity (Obua et al., 2010; Lung and Schaab, 2010). Mabira Central forest reserve (CRF) is facing increasing pressure from a diversity of changing land use/cover types that arise from encroachment; illegal extraction of timber mainly by local communities. The forest is subject to stress particularly, its Eastern compartments (Nabanoga et al., 2010) where tea, sugarcane plantations and factories have been established. The main resultant effects from the enormous threats are deforestation and degradation which have reduced the ecological functions that support the sharing of resources. These include light, temperature, rainfall, wind, humidity, pests and diseases, soil nutrients and spaces (Kayanja & Byarugaba, 2001).

This study has taken note of earlier studies on Mabira Central Forest Reserve (CFR) that have focused more on species diversity, management and economic valuations (Naidoo and Adamawicz 2005, Nature Uganda 2011; Nabanoga et al., 2010). However, there is none on land use/cover change trends in and around Mabira CFR for the last four decades, despite reports of widespread deforestation and degradation. Understanding the socio-economic, political and cultural dynamics of land use/cover changes is very critical for assessing the progress of collaborative management programmes and level exploitation for non-forest consumptive products promoted by the National Forestry Authority. Therefore, the purpose of this study is twofold: (i) to assess the land use / cover changes in and around Mabira Central Forest Reserve over the last four decades (1970-2015) and (ii) to account for drivers of the land use/cover changes during this period.

2.0 Description of study area

The Mabira rain forest, is a central forest reserve covering about 306 square kilometers situated between 32 52° - 33 07° E and 0 24° - 0 35° N straddles the districts of Mukono, Buikwe and Kayunga Districts

(see Fig.1). It is found 54 km East of Kampala and 26 km West of Jinja. The forest reserve is found at an altitude of 1,070 to 1,340 meters above sea level and it's regarded as one of the last remaining rain forests and biggest in Central Uganda. The forest and environs receive an annual rainfall amount of about 1,250 to 1,400 mm. The northern part the forest is dominated by broad, reed-checked rivers, Sezibwa and Musamya, flowing north to Lake Kyoga, while the Nile passes in a 2 km distance away to the North-East. The reserve is a water catchment area for Lake Kyoga and the Victoria Nile. It was first gazetted as a CFR in 1932 and currently it is under the management of National Forestry Authority (NFA) with 65 compartments created by the management plan of 1994/95 and four main management zones: i) the strict nature reserve where no extraction is permitted except for research activities conducted but even then these are under very restrictive measures: ii) the recreation buffer zone which has activities like ecotourism and limited harvesting; iii) production low impact zone where timber harvesting is permitted, and; iv) the production (encroachment) zone where the forest has already been degraded with almost no harvestable timber. Management of the forest has adopted a collaborative management to a few compartments (179, 229, and 171) in order to enhance sustainability of benefits from forest resources.

The reserve has about 27 community enclaves which can easily be mistaken as encroachments. These enclaves, however, have been there before its gazettment as CFR and therefore are legally private land (Nabanoga et al., 2010). These woven-in settlements together with population pressures, poverty, a desire for agricultural expansion, demand for timber, biomass plus the interest by Sugar corporation of Uganda limited (SCOUL) to expand sugar production to almost a quarter of the total area covered by the reserve make the area more susceptible to degradation and deforestation. The population density of Mabira forest area is quite high, ranging from 15,122 people /sq. km in Parishes (BIOTA East Africa 2010). The CFR faces major threats from the persistent encroachments (Uganda NAPA 2007, UNEP, 2004). This may result into desertification, loss of biodiversity, erosion of gene pools, increase vulnerability of local communities to climate extremes, and reduction of livelihood assets.

Fig.1: A map of Mabira and environs

3.0 Materials and Methods

A series of cloud free Landsat TM/ETM+ images were downloaded (<http://glovis.usgs.gov>), pre-processed and analysed to quantify land use/ cover changes (LUCC) in and around Mabira CFR. The Landsat images have a high frequent repeat cycle and available for free download (Alberti et al. 2004; Goetz et al. 2004; and Yang, 2002).The specifications of the Landsat scenes of 1975, 1986, 2000 and 2015 year were download, processed and analyzed to characterize LUCC in and around the forest. The images acquisition and specifications are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Landsat image specifications

<i>Satellite/Sensor</i>	<i>Date</i>	<i>Path</i>	<i>Row</i>	<i>Band No.</i>	<i>Resolution (m)</i>
Landsat MSS	03/01/1975	171	60	3,2,1	60
Landsat TM	28/12/1986	171	60	3,2,1	30
Landsat TM	10/02/2000	171	60	3,2,1	30
Landsat OLI	08/05/2015	171	60	4,3,2	30

The image processing procedures included image pre-processing, image classification, accuracy assessment and analysis of the LUCC. The Landsat images were enhanced using majority-filtering methodology. This improved the spectral reflectance of classes. The

images were also atmospherically corrected using Dark Object Subtraction procedure to minimize the impact of atmosphere on the sensor. The method searches and removes dark pixel values. The Landsat Multi-Spectral Scanner data was geometrically and radiometrically corrected. The images were corrected and resampled, using cubic convolution, to a Universal Transverse Mercator projected (Mas, 1991). The pre-processed images were classified using a hybrid of supervised and unsupervised classification algorithms in ENVI software for spectral reflectance clustering. This algorithm provided land use/cover spectral classes in and around the Central Forest Reserve. Auxiliary data was collected which included ground truth data and topographic maps. The ground Truth data was in the form of reference data points collected using Geographical Positioning System (GPS) for 2015 image analysis, used for image classification and accuracy assessment of the results.

A total of 120 training sites were randomly created and visited for validation purposes prior to post classification; this was important to improve the accuracy of the classification (Harris & Ventura, 1995; Jensen, 2004). A land use and cover reference map of 1986, developed by National Forestry Authority was acquired and utilized to improve on the post classification accuracy. The delineated classes of land use/cover in and around Mabira Central Forest Reserve were; built-upland, plantations, subsistence farming, forest, bush land, open water and wetland (Table 2).

Table 2: Delineated classes of land use /cover

<i>Class name</i>	<i>Description</i>
Built-up	Residential, industrial, transport and communication, recreational
Bush land	Remnants of a disturbed vegetation that is not cultivated but with trees, shrubs and other vegetation
Forest	Extensive with trees and other woody vegetation
Open water	Rivers, ponds,
Plantation	Large scale farming/crop growing
Subsistence farming	Home consumption without any significant surplus for sale
Wetland	Water logged, low lying land areas
Woodland	Low density forest, trees, wood

A multi date Post Classification Comparison algorithm was used to detect and determine changes in land use/cover for three intervals 1975-1986, 1986-2000 and 2000-2015. The detection was performed in ArcGIS 10.1. This is the most common and successful approach to change detection to monitor land use/cover changes because it has a

better and detailed representation of nature with the occurring changes, one can classify and compare images of different dates, recorded under different atmospheric and environmental conditions (Singh 1989; Rivera 2005; Zhou et al. 2008; Warner and Campagna 2009; Yuan et al. 1999; Yuan et al, 2005).

The assessment of land use/cover classification accuracy was twofold: development of an error matrix and validation of classified images using a high resolution image (Sentinel-2) for post classification accuracy. The rectified Sentinel image scene acquired in January 2016 was downloaded, pre-processed and classified using segmentation algorithm which partitioned the image into segments that were later overlaid with the Landsat image for over classification of land use/cover classes' assessment. A total of 120 points were collected from different land use/cover types and used as reference points to develop the image error matrices. An error matrix technique was adopted to compare the likelihood of change of pixel that might change from one class to another class from 1975 to 2015. Overall accuracy, producer's and user's accuracies, as well as Kappa statistics were generated from the error matrices (Table 3). Kappa statistics incorporate classification errors (Rosenfield and Fitzpatrick-Lins1986).

The subsequent land use/cover maps for 1975, 1986, 2000 and 2015 shown in Fig.2 had an overall map accuracy of 100%, 100%, 88.8%, 79% and 76% respectively for all the images by using the error matrix. This approach has been popular in evaluating per-pixel classification (Lu and Weng 2007). Kappa statistics was also computed for each classified map to measure the accuracy of the results for the four years giving 99.4%, 99.1%, 78.3% and 75.4% for the above years respectively. The overall results are viable for subsequent analysis and change detection (Lea and Curtis 2010).

Table 3: A summary of Landsat classification accuracies (%) for 1975, 1986, 2000 and 2015

Land use/cover types	1975		1986		2000		2015	
	Producer's (%)	User's (%)						
Plantations	100	100	100	100	74.0	74	93.2	94
Forest	100	100	100	100	97.0	93	96.1	93
Woodland	100	100	100	100	57.0	74	68.0	57
Open water	100	100	100	100	98.0	92	83.6	94
Built up	100	100	100	100	23.0	61	48.9	48
Wetland	100	100	100	100	69.0	39	56.9	58

Subsistence Farming	100	100	100	100	30.0	30	71.6	72
Bushland	100	100	100	100	21.0	100	45.9	49
Overall accuracy	100		100		79		76	
Kappa statistics	99.4		99.1		78.3		75.4	

Questionnaires designed to gain insights into the drivers of land use and cover change were administered to key informants, who included the NFA, NEMA and other resource beneficiaries (e.g. agriculturalists, lumbers, charcoal burners, and brick makers). Focus group discussions were also held for an in-depth understanding of these drivers and their implications for people’s livelihoods. A cross-sectional design approach was used, research tools were administered and different household communities in and around the Mabira CFR. A total of 120 households were randomly selected and interviewed from their homesteads using the local leader’s lists. The districts from which respondents were selected included: Buikwe, Kayunga, and Mukono. 40 households were selected and interviewed from each district. In addition, 5 focus group discussions were conducted in the selected districts, each comprising at least 12 respondents. This permitted free interaction and discussion of issues and concerns regarding the management of the forest. The socio-economic dataset derived was coded in SPSS software and subjected to a logistic regression to classify the most significant drivers of land use/cover in and around the Mabira CFR.

4.0 Results

4.1 Quantification of land use/cover changes (1970-2015)

Results show a total area of 876.6 square kilometers studied and the individual class coverage area and change statistics for 1975, 1986, 2000 and 2015 in tables 4 and 5 respectively.

Fig 2. Land use/cover classification from 1975-2015 for Mabira Central Forest Region

Table 4: Land use/cover statistics

Land use / land cover	1975		1986		2000		2015	
	Area (sqk m)	%	Area (sqk m)	%	Area (sqkm)	%	Area (sqk m)	%
Built-up	3.19	0.36	14.72	1.68	20.84	2.38	45.02	5.14
Bush land	109.90	12.54	96.68	11.03	100.68	11.48	78.23	8.92
Forest	291.60	33.27	273.81	31.23	322.59	36.80	282.35	32.21
Open water	4.28	0.49	3.19	0.36	2.80	0.32	3.93	0.45
Plantation	19.05	2.17	24.94	2.85	62.91	7.18	77.76	8.87
Subsistence farming	127.34	14.53	248.60	28.36	300.69	34.30	285.55	32.57
Wetland	241.45	27.54	188.52	21.51	63.62	7.26	98.18	11.20
Wood land	79.79	9.10	26.15	2.98	2.47	0.28	5.59	0.64
TOTAL	876.60	100.00	876.60	100.00	876.60	100.00	876.60	100.00

The data is for sampled years as a percentage of the total are of 876.6 square kilometers. NB. All digits are rounded off to the nearest decimal point.

Table 5: Land use / cover change statistics from 1975-2015.

Land use / land cover	1975-1986 change		1986-2000 change		2000-2015 change	
	Area (sqk m)	%	Area (sqkm)	%	Area (sqkm)	%
Built-up	11.53	1.32	6.12	0.70	24.18	2.76
Bush land	-13.22	-1.51	4.00	0.46	-22.45	-
Forest	-17.80	-2.03	48.79	5.56	-40.24	-
Open water	-1.09	-0.12	-0.39	-0.04	1.13	0.12
Plantation	5.89	0.67	37.97	4.33	14.85	1.69
Subsistence farming	121.26	13.83	52.09	5.94	-15.14	-
Wetland	-52.93	-6.04	-124.90	-14.25	3.94	0.45
Wood land	-53.64	-6.12	-23.68	-2.70	3.12	0.36

The percentage area of each class from the years of study showed that forest had the largest share in 1975, 1986 and 2000 representing 33.27%, 31.23% and 36.8% respectively total classes assigned. Forest

is mainly in the protected area dominated by semi-deciduous plants as well as a few papyrus (*Cyperus papyrus*) swamps in the wide shallow valleys. This class faced a major reduction of 4.59% (40.24 sq. km) between 2000-2015. The study demonstrated that forest degradation is unidirectional because most of the forest disturbances occurred on the periphery of the Lake Victoria Basin where sugarcane out-growers were more protruding, especially in Kayunga District than in areas where industrialized sugarcane plantations existed. Remote and inaccessible areas had more signs of forest disturbances that were as a result of extraction of timber, charcoal production and encroachment for crop growing land in the same district.

The other classes which faced remarkable decline during the study period were: Wetland 14.25% (124.9 sq. km) between 1986-2000 and woodland loss of 6.12% (53.64 sq. km) between 1975 and 1986. The wetland comprises mainly forest swamps, palms and thicket, papyrus swamp and marshes. The fluctuations realized in Open water class were not very significant. Further changes occurred in Bushland with a reduction of 1.51% between 1975-1986 and 2.56% between 2000-2015; however from 1986-2000 this class gains by 0.46%.

Land use/cover statistics (Table 4) reveal that built-up and plantation lands increase across the years. The plantations include: sugarcane, tea and coffee. Subsistence farming also gained in all the years except in 2015. Built up and plantation classes faced an increase in the total share with built up area increasing from 0.36% in 1975 to 5.14% in 2015, while plantations increased from 2.17% to 8.87% in 2015.

Subsistence farming (comprising of crops like bananas, sweet potatoes, cassava) also increased steadily from 1975 to 2000; it, however, realized an insignificant decline of 1.73% between 2000 and 2015. Agricultural expansion is by far the leading land use associated with nearly all deforestation cases. From the three districts sampled, field statistics revealed that more than 80% of the population is highly dependent on agriculture. It was also noted that land for subsistence farming dominates commercial (plantations) for all years as drawn from Tables 4 and 5).

The changes in land use/cover are represented with negative and positive numbers demonstrating loss or gain in class respectively as illustrated in Table 5. Significant loss is seen to occur in wetlands between 1975-2000 while between 2000- 2015, the greatest loss is

realized in forest. Gain is seen to occur between 1975-2000 and 2000-2015 in subsistence farmlands and built-up classes, respectively.

Pathways of change for the different cover classes are illustrated in Figure 3. A greater loss in wetlands and woodlands can be attributed to an expansion in subsistence farmlands for the years between 1975-1986 and 1986-2000. Furthermore, the loss in forest between 1986-2000 is seen to go to subsistence farming. Despite the gains in subsistence farmlands, a loss is noted between 2000 and 2015 in this class (-1.73%), with a bigger conversion of this to the bushland class. In the same period, there is a remarkable decrease in forest cover (-4.59%), mainly converted to bushlands.

Fig 3: Observed Path ways for the different classes of LUCC

Subsistence

Built up

Woodland

Bushland

Forest

Plantation

Wetland

Open water

4.2 Drivers of land use and cover changes

For the evaluation of underlying drivers of the land use and cover change, a regression analysis was performed of categories using selected socio-economic, political and environmental variables. A number of drivers that explain LUCC were identified. Dominating the broad category of drivers is a combination of social, economic, policy and institutional factors. Logistic regression results revealed that the major drivers of land use and cover change in and around the forest were: the high household size ($P < 0.05$), loss of soil fertility ($P < 0.05$), poor agricultural practices ($P < 0.05$), establishment of roadside markets ($P < 0.05$), industrialization ($P < 0.05$), and unclear forestry boundary ($P < 0.05$), while the non-significant drivers included the low education levels, establishment of power grids, insecurity, political interference and weak enforcement of environmental laws (see Figure 4).

Fig 4: Drivers of land use and cover change

The driver of LUCC and their magnitude are not static but change with time and space with insignificant drivers in the 1970s becoming significant drivers by 2015. The trend of the drivers illustrated in Fig.4 above has also changed with time; statistics reveal that between 1975 and 1986 insecurity (54%) and low education (43%) were significant drivers of LUCC. The high levels of insecurity called

for forest clearances with a fear of their harboring rebels from the government opposition side. The central region where this study took place has experienced political stability and hence improved security for over the last 25 years. Also the levels of sensitization over environmental conservation measures have improved with time, hence education and insecurity becoming insignificant drivers by 2015. The household and population sizes were still low in the 1970s compared to the current statistics; it is, therefore, not surprising to note the shift in their magnitude as driving forces with time.

This study reveals household size (57%) as one of the current significant drivers of LUCC. It was noted that the region has high population densities ranging from 15,122 people /sq km in some Parishes (BIOTA East Africa 2010), which emanate from the high birth rates and migrations. This has called for a need to expand agricultural land to feed the growing population, as well as, extending land for settlement. Poor agricultural practices (69%) and the loss of soil fertility (63%) have led to further encroachments in search of fertile lands for cultivation. However, considering the poor farming methods, the newly cultivated lands tend to lose fertility in a few years prompting more clearance. The desire for industrialization, as a strategy for development being adopted by most developing countries, has been another driving force for LUCC ranking at (52%) by 2015.

It is important to note that part of the Mabira CFR is along the Kampala-Jinja road, which is a strategic location for businesses. Off road side markets (49%) have been established for economic benefits; forest extractors find it convenient to transport their products because of its proximity to the city. The area is therefore attracting populations to meet their social-economic demands, hence undergoing a lot of degradation considering the weak management efforts.

The unclear forest boundary, plus the mix of private and public land ownership, with the inadequate supervisory and monitoring team for the Mabira CFR, has increased uncontrolled encroachments, exploitation and illegal timber extraction.

5.0 Discussion

The drivers of change in and around Mabira CFR are attributed to social, economic, political and institutional factors. Basing on the four

land use/cover maps analysis, despite forest being the dominant class, its loss is realized between 1975-1986 and 2000-2015. Results here confirm the earlier studies by (Lung and Schaab 2008) showing a significant decrease in forest cover in the area. Forest loss between 1975-1986 is ascribed to heavy deforestation, encroachments and settlements, partly arising from government decision to introduce a double crop regime and civil unrest. It was noted that encroachers took advantage of the then prevailing situations, where politicians could not intervene for fear to lose popularity. To this, more encroachment was seen in the eastern blocks of the forest compartments. Similar drivers have been sighted by Howard (1991). More forest loss which is realized between 2000 and 2015 is in agreement with earlier research by (Waiswa 2011; UBOS 2002, 2008, 2012) where forest loss is attributed to the growing population in the region and conversion to agriculture (FAO 2016). Datasets from the present study reveal an average of 9 members per household in 2015 compared to the average number of 7 by the Forest Department Census (1987). The growing numbers coupled with the high poverty levels and a lack of livelihood diversification into non-agricultural activities has mainly raised demand for agriculture and firewood energy. The findings reinforce the assertion by (USDA Forest Service 2004; Ngo et al., 2003) that population expansion is a key driver for land use/cover change.

It was, however, noted that between 1986-2000, the forest class gains coverage resulting from government eviction of forest encroachers which was effective in the late 1980's (Aluma, 1989; Bahati et al., 2008; Nabanoga et al., 2010). It is also noted that due to the undervaluation of the resource, the real price of charcoal fell by 50% between 1989-1994 (Kayanja and Byaruhanga 2001).

Another important driver for the shrinking of the forest land is the unclear boundary of Mabira CFR together with the mix of private and public land ownership; this has increased uncontrolled exploitation and illegal timber extraction. Resulting from this has been the rapid degradation of the Eastern part of the forest. Findings from this study conform to earlier research by (Aide et al., 2013; Waiswa 2011; Lambin et al., 2010; Kayanja and Byaruhanga, 2001) who have identified that forest encroachments and management confusions are subsequent to undefined demarcations. Subsistence farming also expanded for all the years except in 2015 where it lost 1.73%; the gain in subsistence farming is expected, as a response to the growing population. Howard (1991) also notes the expansion of densely populated agricultural lands, especially along the forest

boundaries. This expansion is also explained by gaps in the management and monitoring processes. From the study, it is noted that one NFA official monitors and supervises a minimum of 10 compartments. It is, therefore, not surprising to note from this study that a bigger portion of woodland and wetlands between 1975-2000 were transformed into farmlands. The results are consistent with earlier studies by (U.N. FAO 2005 and 2010) highlighting Uganda's deforestation rate of 1.86% per year between 1990 and 2010. The study further reveals that policy failures, weak implementation of laws and regulations and attempts to degazette parts of Mabira CFR continue to be vital drivers of land use/cover change. Jagger (2010) denotes that corruption was common in harvesting valuable forest products in both central and local forest reserves in western Uganda. (Vogt et al., 2005; Banana et al., 2005) also highlight government contribution to Mabira disturbances. It was noted from the focus group discussions that there has been a lack of political will to uphold the existing laws and policies. Institutions like the National forestry authority (NFA) and the National environment management authority (NEMA) are understaffed, making it hard to manage specific environmental resources. It is also important to note that the reserve has 27 built-up enclaves and is surrounded by sugarcane plantations that are seen to expand steadily during the study period. Studies elsewhere have pinned illegal logging to ill-defined policies and weak institutional enforcement (Jepson et al., 2001).

The present study also notes that built-up areas and plantations expanded considerably over the period of study. This stems from the poor government decisions right from the mid-1970s where double agricultural production was encouraged and the declaration of free settlement for Ugandans in any part of the country (Hamilton 1984). It was noted that most of the agro-based industries within the region like tea processing, tobacco curing and sugar production require a lot of firewood. The government also continued to encourage forest encroachment by providing facilities like schools and hospitals to the illegal settlers (Orsdol 1986). Such developments have made the reserve highly susceptible to encroachments for firewood and construction materials. The study notes disturbances affecting the forest reserve with built up lands spreading to the north of the forest, and the west being cleared for sugarcane plantations, as also observed by (Mitchell 2010). The central parts of the forest, however, remain intact, probably due to the collaborative management efforts, establishment of management zones with defined activities and high restriction measures.

Another land use/cover that has undergone remarkable changes is the wetland class, between 1975-2000, during which period a decline of up to 14.25% is noticeable. This decline is attributed to the massive encroachments resulting from the evictions from the forests of 1988-1989 (Aluma, 1989; Bahati et al., 2008; Nabanoga et al., 2010). The observed changes are line with (Tejuoso, 2006) by encroachers, particularly for subsistence farming. However between 2000 and 2015, a gain of 0.45% in wetlands, resulting from community sensitization to minimize wetland degradation, strict enforcement of the wetland policy and community collaboration attempts to enhance wetland conservation. Similar gains in wetland coverage in the same observation period have been reported by (Aryamanya, 2011).

6.0 Conclusion and recommendations

The present study employed image processing techniques in the assessment of land use/cover changes and their change detection. It is evident from the study that Mabira CFR is of social economic and ecological value and that the forest is at threat of the expanding encroachments and degradation. The conversion of most classes to agriculture continues to pose threats to the environment because it is associated with heavy deforestation and degradation. These encroachments are particularly from the forest boundaries and the existing enclaves within the reserve and this is increasingly impacting on the areas within the reserve boundary and its functioning. Major driving forces of land use cover change are: population expansion, loss of soil fertility, poor agricultural practices, establishment of roadside markets, industrialization and unclear forestry boundary.

Forest degradation has become of concern considering the negative impacts it has on biodiversity conservation. Although the deforestation rates in the strict nature reserve management zone of Mabira CFR are highly controlled, pressure in the other zones is relatively high. There is need to intensify the monitoring process and have well defined forest boundaries or demarcations. Considering the huge sizes of compartments in the forest, it is also necessary that staff are recruited and trained to effectively patrol the region. There is need to sell and embrace the idea of collaborative forest management (CFM) considering the benefits enjoyed in the very few compartments where it has been adopted. CFM will minimize the current tension between the NFA officials and the forest communities. Share feedback information from prior research done, have the communities aware of the state of their environment, know

the rights and responsibilities of forest users. Mapping and quantifying forest resources is needed to guide policy makers and implementers, this study recommends the application of remote sensing and GIS to easily capture data for extensive regions as well as monitoring of potential risk areas due to the changes that may have surfaced.

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